

Response and Breeding of Wheat under Drought Stress

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Drought is one of the most significant factors that affects agricultural productivity and output. Crops respond to drought stress in a variety of ways, including morphological, physiological, biochemical, and molecular responses. Drought stress has a significant impact on the vegetative and reproductive phases of plants. Drought tolerance is a complex feature governed by polygenes, whose expression is affected by a variety of environmental factors. This implies that breeding for this trait is extremely challenging, and novel molecular techniques like as molecular markers, QTL mapping procedures, and gene expression patterns should be used to create drought-tolerant genotypes. During drought stress, wheat has multiple genes that are responsible for drought stress tolerance and generate several enzymes and proteins, such as late embryogenesis abundant (lea), responsive to abscisic acid (Rab), rubisco, helicase, proline, glutathione-S-transferase (GST), and carbohydrates (Nezhadahmadi *et al.*, 2013).

Physiological response under drought

Closure of stomata, decrease in photosynthesis activity, development of oxidative stress, alteration in cell wall integrity, production of toxic metabolites that cause plant death (Bray *et al.*, 2002), signal recognition of roots, turgor loss and adjustment of osmosis, reduction in water potential of leaf, decrease in stomata conductance to CO₂, reduction of internal CO₂ concentration, and reduction of growth rates are some of the physiological responses. Various investigators investigated membrane integrity and its impact under water stress while determining drought resistance (Premachandra *et al.*, 1990 and Deshmukh *et al.*, 1991). According to Grudkowska *et al.*, 2004, cysteine proteinase is important in plant signalling pathways, growth and development, and the response to many types of stress. In wheat leaf organs, cysteine is expressed, and its contribution to proteolysis activity increases during drought Zagdanska *et al.*, 1996.

Biochemical response under drought

Biochemical responses include reduced photochemical efficiency, reduced Rubisco efficiency, the accumulation of stress metabolites (glutathione, MDHA, glybet, and polyamines), antioxidative enzymes (superoxide dismutase (SOD), peroxidase (POD), catalase (CAT), ascorbate peroxidase (APX), glutathione reductase (GR), glutathione-S-transferase (GST), glutathione peroxidase (GP)), monodehydroascorbate reductase (MDHAR), and reduced reactive oxygen species (ROS) accumulation (Nezhadahmadi *et al.*, 2013). Evidence suggests that drought induces oxidative damage in plants due to increased formation of ROS and a deficient antioxidant defence mechanism (Chen *et al.*, 2004). Wheat genotypes with stronger osmotic regulators and lower malondialdehyde (MDA) content have superior drought tolerance, according to numerous research (Chen *et al.*, 2004). Higher amounts of polyamines, according to Malabika *et al.*, 2001, can help crops grow faster under water-stressed environments.

Morphological response under drought

Drought resistance has been linked to early maturity, small plant size, and decreased leaf area, according to Rizza *et al.*, 2004. Under drought stress, Lonbani *et al.*, 2011 stated that the length and area of the wheat flag leaf grew while the breadth remained same. According to Rucker *et al.*, 1995, dryness reduces leaf area, which reduces photosynthesis. Water stress can also reduce the number of leaves per plant, leaf size, and leaf lifespan (Shao *et al.*, 2008). Drought stress causes the root to be the first organ to be affected (Shimazaki *et al.*, 2005). Under moderate and severe drought circumstances, the rate of development of wheat roots was slowed (Noctor *et al.*, 1998).

Molecular response under drought

Some genes, such as dehydrins (Close *et al.*, 1996), vacuolar acid invertase (Trouverie *et al.*, 2003), glutathione S-transferase (GST) (Anderson *et al.*, 2004), and late embryo abundant (LEA) protein (Pnueli *et al.*, 2002), are known to be drought influenced and produce various types of drought stress related proteins and enzymes; expression of ABA genes and production of proteins like RAB, rubisco, helicase, proline, and carbohydrates are the molecular basis of drought tolerance. According to Sivamani *et al.*, 2000, the *HVA1* gene aids in wheat development during drought stress. Kam *et al.*, 2007 discovered the genes responsible for water stress in wheat. They discovered that *TaRZF70*, a RING-H2 zinc finger gene, was increased in the leaf and downregulated in the root in response to drought stress (Seki *et al.*, 2003).

Breeding for drought tolerance in wheat

- 1. Through Conventional and Biotechnological Breeding methods-** The discovery of genetic diversity under drought across plant genotypes or sexually compatible cultivars, as well as the introduction of tolerance lines with appropriate agronomic features, are required in traditional breeding. Traditional breeding procedures are labour-intensive, requiring significant effort to distinguish undesired features from desirable traits, which is not cost-effective. The enhancement of resistant plants by genetic engineering, on the other hand, necessitates the identification of essential genetic dominants in order to react as stress resistance crops by introducing novel genes into plants. Drought influences the activity of a large number of genes, and gene expression tests have revealed that drought stress induces and represses the expression of a number of genes (Sahi *et al.*, 2006). Many drought stress-induced genes have been discovered and cloned. Drought-resistant germplasm can be improved through crop genetic engineering and molecular-marker approaches (Gosala *et al.*, 2009).
- 2. Through molecular markers-** QTL mappings for senescence of flag leaf (FLS) in normal and water-stressed conditions in winter wheat have been examined using amplified fragment length polymorphism (AFLP) and simple sequence repeat (SSR) markers. The gene responsible for this trait has been identified, and a QTL has been discovered on chromosome 2D linked to enhanced drought performance (Verma *et al.*, 2004). Some markers in durum wheat have been connected to grain production and morphophysiological drought resistance features (Nachit *et al.*, 1993). Milad *et al.*, 2011 discovered RAPD and ISSR markers linked to the flag leaf senescence gene in drought-stressed wheat. RAPDs have been demonstrated to be useful as genetic markers in hexaploid wheat (Joshi *et al.*, 1996).

Fig: The effect of drought stress on wheat (Nezhadahmadi et al., 2013).

Conclusion

The detection of plant genomic responses to water stress is critical. To begin, it compiles extensive data on plant transcriptional responses to drought stress. Second, it allows researchers to learn about gene functioning under stressful situations. Third, it aids in the identification of stress-responsive promoters and associated cis-elements, which are both important for basic research and crop engineering (Zhou et al., 2007). Drought tolerance can be improved quickly by modifying the genes responsible for plant growth regulators, antioxidants, proteins, and transcriptional factors (Gupta et al., 1999). QTL analysis and molecular mapping are two other effective ways for determining qualitative and quantitative features, such as stress resistance.

Reference

- Anderson, J. V., and Davis, D. G. (2004). "Abiotic stress alters transcript profiles and activity of glutathione S-transferase, glutathione peroxidase, and glutathione reductase in *Euphorbia esula*," *Plant Physiology*, vol. 120, no. 3, pp. 421–433.
- Bray, E. A. (2002). "Classification of genes differentially expressed during water-deficit stress in *Arabidopsis thaliana*: an analysis using microarray and differential expression data," *Annals of Botany*, vol. 89, pp. 803–811.

- Chen, Z. and Gallie, D. R. (2004). "The ascorbic acid redox state controls guard cell signaling and stomatal movement," *Plant Cell*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1143–1162.
- Close, T. J. (1996). "Dehydrins: emergence of a biochemical role of a family of plant dehydration proteins," *Physiologia Plantarum*, vol. 97, no. 4, pp. 795–803.
- Deshmukh, P. S., Sairam, R. K., and Shukla, D. S. (1991). "Measurement of ion leakage as a screening technique for drought resistance in wheat genotypes," *Indian Journal of Plant Physiology*, vol. 35, pp. 89–91.
- Gosala, S. S., Wania, H. S., and Kanga, M. S. (2009). "Biotechnology and drought tolerance," *Journal of Crop Improvement*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 19–54.
- Grudkowska, M. and Zagdanska, B. (2004). "Multifunctional role of plant cysteine proteinases," *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 609–624.
- Gupta, P. K., Varshney, R. K., Sharma, P. C., and Ramesh, B. (1999). "Molecular markers and their applications in wheat breeding," *Plant Breeding*, vol. 118, no. 5, pp. 369–390.
- Joshi, C. P., and Nguyen, H. T. (1996). "Differential display-mediated rapid identification of different members of a multigene family, *HSP16.9* in wheat," *Plant Molecular Biology*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 575–584.
- Kam, J., Gresshoff, P., Shorter, R., and Xue, G.-P. (2007). "Expression analysis of RING zinc finger genes from *Triticum aestivum* and identification of *TaRZF70* that contains four RING-H2 domains and differentially responds to water deficit between leaf and root," *Plant Science*, vol. 173, no. 6, pp. 650–659.
- Lonbani, M. and Arzani, A. (2011). "Morpho-physiological traits associated with terminal drought stress tolerance in triticale and wheat," *Agronomy Research*, vol. 9, no. 1-2, pp. 315–329.
- Malabika, R., and Wu, R. (2001). "Arginine decarboxylase transgene expression and analysis of environmental stress tolerance in transgenic rice," *Plant Science*, vol. 160, no. 5, pp. 869–875.
- Milad, S. I., Wahba, L. E., and Barakat, M. N. (2011). "Identification of RAPD and ISSR markers associated with flag leaf senescence under water-stressed conditions in wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.)," *Australian Journal of Crop Science*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 337–343.
- Nachit, M. M., Baum, M., Autrique, E., Sorrells, M. E., Ali Dib, T., and Monneveux, P. (1993). "Association of morphophysiological traits with RFLP markers in durum wheat," in *Tolerance à la Sécheresse des Cereales en Zone Mediterran eenne*, P. Monneveux and M. Ben Salem, Eds., pp. 159–171, Diversite G´ en´ etique et ´ Amelioration Varietale, Montpellier, France.
- Nezhadahmadi, A., Prodha, Z. H., and Faruq, G. (2013). Drought Tolerance in Wheat. *The Scientific World Journal*, Vol 2013, pp 1-12.
- Noctor, G., and Foyer, C. H. (1998). "Ascorbate and glutathione: keeping active oxygen under control," *Annual Review of Plant Physiology and Plant Molecular Biology*, vol. 49, pp. 249–279.
- Pnueli, L., Hallak-Herr, E., Rozenberg, M. et al., (2002). "Molecular and biochemical mechanisms associated with dormancy and drought tolerance in the desert legume *Retama raetam*," *Plant Journal*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 319–330.
- Premachandra, G. S., Saneoka, H., and Ogata, S. (1990). "Cell membrane stability an indicator of drought tolerance as affected by applied nitrogen in soybean," *Journal of Agricultural Science*, vol. 115, pp. 63–66.

- Rizza, F., Badeck, F. W., Cattivelli, L., Lidestri, O., di Fonzo, N., and Stanca, A. M. (2004). "Use of a water stress index to identify barley genotypes adapted to rainfed and irrigated conditions," *Crop Science*, vol. 44, no. 6, pp. 2127–2137.
- Rucker, K. S., Kevin, C. K., Holbrook, C. C., and Hook, J. E. (1995). "Identification of peanut genotypes with improved drought avoidance traits," *Peanut Science*, vol. 22, pp. 14–18.
- Sahi, C., Singh, A., Blumwald, E., and Grover, A. (2006). "Beyond osmolytes and transporters: novel plant salt-stress tolerance related genes from transcriptional profiling data," *Physiologia Plantarum*, vol. 127, no. 1, pp. 1–9.
- Seki, M., Kamei, A., Yamaguchi-Shinozaki, K., and Shinozaki, K. (2003). "Molecular responses to drought, salinity and frost: common and different paths for plant protection," *Current Opinion in Biotechnology*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 194–199.
- Shao, H. B., Chu, L. Y., Jaleel, C. A., and Zhao, C. X. (2008). "Water-deficit stress-induced anatomical changes in higher plants," *Comptes Rendus*, vol. 331, no. 3, pp. 215–225.
- Shimazaki, Y., Ookawa, T., and Hirasawa, T. (2005). "The root tip and accelerating region suppress elongation of the decelerating region without any effects on cell turgor in primary roots of maize under water stress," *Plant Physiology*, vol. 139, no. 1, pp. 458–465.
- Sivamani, E., Bahieldin, A., Wraith, J. M. et al., (2000). "Improved biomass productivity and water use efficiency under water deficit conditions in transgenic wheat constitutively expressing the barley *HVA1* gene," *Plant Science*, vol. 155, no. 1, pp. 1–9.
- Trouverie, J., Thevenot, C., Rocher, J. P., Sotta, B., and Prioul, J. L. (2003). "The role of abscisic acid in the response of a specific vacuolar invertase to water stress in the adult maize leaf," *Journal of Experimental Botany*, vol. 54, no. 390, pp. 2177–2186.
- Verma, V., Foulkes, M. J., Worland, A. J., Sylvester-Bradley, R., Caligari, P. D. S., and Snape, J. W. (2004). "Mapping quantitative trait loci for flag leaf senescence as a yield determinant in winter wheat under optimal and drought-stressed environments," *Euphytica*, vol. 135, no. 3, pp. 255–263.
- Zagdanska, B. and Wi, K. (1996). "sniewski, "Endoproteinase activities in wheat leaves upon water deficit," *Acta Biochimica Polonica*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 515–520.
- Zhou, J., Wang, X., Jiao, Y. et al., (2007). "Global genome expression analysis of rice in response to drought and high-salinity stresses in shoot, flag leaf, and panicle," *Plant Molecular Biology*, vol. 63, no. 5, pp. 591–608.